

Epidemiology and causes of preterm birth

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1. Article summary

This paper is the first in a three-part series on preterm birth, which is the leading cause of perinatal morbidity and mortality in developed countries. Infants are born preterm at less than 37 weeks.

The introduction: Contains the **first figure**, which concerns the premature birth rate in the USA. Its purpose is to show the increase in premature births from 1981 to 2004. It shows that this increase occurred despite the advancement of medicine. This allows us to investigate the epidemiology, causes and mechanisms leading to preterm birth.

Epidemiology: The **second figure** shows the epidemiology of preterm births, taking into account different mechanisms. The figure shows that spontaneous preterm birth is the most common. Preterm births can also be classified according to the duration of pregnancy. The **third figure** shows both the percentage of preterm births and the risk factors that cause preterm birth in the United States from 1989 to 2001. The number of births caused by medical factors has been increasing over the years. This paragraph also provides the definition and mechanism of preterm birth and PROM.

Risk factors: This paragraph covers the mechanism and types of risk factors causing preterm birth. The factors are divided into groups such as maternal demographic characteristics, nutritional status, pregnancy history, present pregnancy characteristics, psychological characteristics, adverse behaviours, infection, uterine contractions and cervical length, and biological and genetic markers.

Maternal risk factors: It has been reported that in the USA and UK black women are at greater risk of preterm birth than women of other races. The risk of PTB is also influenced by socioeconomic status, maternal age and education. The influence of medical factors and previous births is also described. **Figure four** shows the influence of maternal BMI on spontaneous and induced labor. PTB is more common in mothers with a low BMI. It also describes how BMI affects the fetus and labor.

Pregnancy history: The authors emphasize that previous PTBs influence the occurrence of subsequent PTBs in the future.

Pregnancy characteristics: This paragraph illustrates the different factors that cause the possibility of PTB. These include twin pregnancies, bleeding and hemorrhage, placental abruption, high stress, clinical depression, smoking during and before pregnancy. **Figure five** illustrates the different routes of intrauterine infection such as intraamniotic infection, intrauterine infection, and vaginal infection. Infection can also be caused by sexually transmitted diseases.

Biological and genetic markers: This paragraph describes studies that show the influence of inflammation, hormones, genes on the prediction and occurrence of preterm labor. The most important factor is fetal fibronectin, a glycoprotein that when present in cervicovaginal fluid is a marker of choriodecidual disruption.

2. Figures and results

- Contains the **first figure**, which concerns the premature birth rate in the USA. Its purpose is to show the increase in premature births from 1981 to 2004. It shows that this increase occurred despite the advancement of medicine. This allows us to investigate the epidemiology, causes and mechanisms leading to preterm birth.
- The **second figure** shows the epidemiology of preterm births, taking into account different mechanisms. The figure shows that spontaneous preterm birth is the most common. Preterm births can also be classified according to the duration of pregnancy.

- The **third figure** shows both the percentage of preterm births and the risk factors that cause preterm birth in the United States from 1989 to 2001. The number of births caused by medical factors has been increasing over the years.
- **Figure four** shows the influence of maternal BMI on spontaneous and induced labor. PTB is more common in mothers with a low BMI. It also describes how BMI affects the fetus and labor.
- **Figure five** illustrates the different routes of intrauterine infection such as intraamniotic infection, intrauterine infection, and vaginal infection.

3. Authors

Dr Robert L. Goldenberg (h-index: 111)

is a preeminent figure in Obstetrics and Gynecology, has improved the understanding of syndromes responsible for maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality, with a particular emphasis on the circumstances responsible for preterm birth, fetal growth restriction, and fetal death. He has a keen interest in the social determinants of health and disease, especially in the southern United States and in low- and middle-income countries. His work has provided important insight into the prediction of spontaneous preterm birth; the role of antenatal steroids in inducing fetal maturity; and the determinants of fetal death, fetal growth restriction, and virtually every other “great obstetrical syndrome.”

Prof. Roberto Romero (h-index: 157)

is the Chief of the Perinatology Research Branch, Program and Division Director for Perinatal Research and Obstetrics in the Division of Intramural Research at NICHD/NIH. He is also the Editor-in-Chief of the *American Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology* and *Ultrasound in Obstetrics and Gynecology*. Roberto Romero is an outstanding researcher and educator in the fields of ectopic pregnancy diagnosis, prenatal diagnosis, amniocentesis, and infections as causes of preterm birth and cerebral palsy.

Jennifer Culhane (h-index: 46)

is a specialist in the field of medicine who works at Yale School of Medicine. She is affiliated with the Department of Medicine, where she conducts research and clinical practice, particularly in the areas of public health, infectious diseases, and preventive medicine. Her research interests include the impact of social and environmental factors on population health, as well as improving access to healthcare in economically disadvantaged communities.

Prof. Jay D. Iams (h-index: 78)

is a renowned specialist in obstetrics and gynecology, affiliated with The Ohio State University Wexner Medical Center. He is a professor in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology and is one of the leading experts in high-risk pregnancy care, including preterm birth and pregnancy-related disorders. His research focuses on improving maternal and neonatal health outcomes, particularly for those at high risk. Prof. Iams is also involved in studies on the prevention of preterm labor and methods for monitoring pregnancy. His clinical expertise includes providing care for pregnant patients and performing complex medical procedures related to high-risk pregnancies. Prof. Iams also plays a significant role in medical education, training future physicians and specialists in obstetrics and gynecology, and leads various research and educational projects in the field.

4. Journal

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